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ПРОСУВАННЯ ПОСЛУГ ЕКСПОРТУ ВИЩОЇ ОСВІТИ В СУЧАСНИХ УМОВАХ: ДОСВІД ЛАТВІЇ

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PROMOTION OF HIGHER EDUCATION EXPORT SERVICES IN MODERN CONDITIONS: EXPERIENCE OF LATVIA

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Анотація

В статті проаналізовано поняття та сутність експорту освіти, визначено особливості експорту освіти в сучасних умовах трансформаційної економіки світу. Досліджено особливості експорту вищої освіти в Латвії та визначено механізми просування експорту освіти. Визначено основні світові тенденції розвитку експорту вищої освіти, проведено оцінку потенціалу експорту вищої освіти Латвії та можливості використання досвіду латвійських закладів вищої освіти в Україні. Проведено оцінку ефективності маркетингових інструментів просування експорту освіти та створення бренду закладу вищої освіти.

Abstract

The article analyzes the concept and essence of the export of education, defines the peculiarities of the export of education in the modern conditions of the transformational economy of the world. The peculiarities of the export of higher education in Latvia have been studied and the mechanisms of promoting the export of education have been determined. The main global trends in the development of the export of higher education have been determined, an assessment of the export potential of Latvian higher education and the possibility of using the experience of Latvian higher education institutions in Ukraine has been carried out. The evaluation of the effectiveness of marketing tools for promoting the export of education and creating a brand of a higher education institution was carried out.

Ключові слова: експорт освіти, вища освіта, інтернаціоналізація, трансформація економіки.

Keywords: export of education, higher education, internationalization, economic transformation.

The export market of educational services plays one of the key roles in the modern world economy. In the struggle for a place in the world market of educational services, along with such countries as the USA, Great Britain, France and Germany, the Baltic countries, especially Latvia, also participate. High competition of the world's leading universities for talented, highly motivated foreign applicants, as well as the globally developing situation with the coronavirus pandemic, have forced Latvian higher education institutions to master new tools for building an attractive image and a competitive university brand in conditions of self-isolation at an unprecedented pace. Traditional marketing methods for building and promoting the brand of a higher education institution in the context of the global corona crisis are no longer enough, and therefore the communication strategy tools for attracting target stakeholders in the international market of

educational services have expanded to include digital technologies. As a result, digital internationalization has become a significant tool for creating and maintaining an attractive image of Latvia's scientific and educational potential for foreign applicants.

The internationalization of higher education is a relatively new phenomenon that is rapidly becoming the most important trend in the development of national education systems around the world. The internationalization of education should be understood as a process in which the tasks, goals, functions and the organization of the provision of educational services to various target groups acquire an international dimension, characterized by political, economic, social and technological factors [1]. Among its main areas are traditionally distinguished: academic mobility of students and faculty, mobility of educational programs and institutional mobility, the introduction of international educational

standards, the creation of a multilingual educational environment, open and distance learning through massive open online courses implemented on national and international online platforms. The internationalization of higher education is inextricably linked with the education export strategy, which is seen as a soft power tool that determines the position of the state in socio-cultural and geopolitical space, a method of attracting and retaining talents from abroad and obtaining export income [2,3]. In recent years, the export of education has become one of the strategic sources of profit for countries such as the USA, Great Britain, Australia, France, and Germany. To date, the number of students in the world studying abroad reaches 6 million people, and the income from their education is approximately \$ 200 billion a year. According to the US Institute for International Education, in 2022, 1.1 million foreign students studied at US colleges and universities, which brought the country's budget \$44.7 billion. About 460,000 foreign students studied in the United Kingdom, and income from the export of educational services made up 26 billion dollars. Education of foreign citizens annually brings Australia an income in the amount of 16.7 billion dollars [3]. The leading exporting countries of education in the world in the pre-pandemic period were China (about 20% of the total number of foreign students worldwide) and India (7% of the total number of foreign students worldwide) [3].

However, modern universities compete not only for income from the export of education, but also for attracting talented young people to the national labor market. Human capital every year is becoming an increasingly important tool for the economic development of modern states. At the same time, it should be noted that national strategies for the development of the internationalization of higher education, despite the relevance of the issue, they are not distinguished by a high degree of elaboration. According to the Central European University (CEU) think tank, 80% of countries (158 out of 198) for 2020 did not have a national strategy for the internationalization of higher education. 11% of countries (22 out of 198) had a formal strategy for the internationalization of higher education, the remaining 9% of countries (18 of 198) mentioned the internationalization of education as part of the overall higher education strategy. At the same time, all existing strategies have been developed and published over the past 5–10 years [7].

First the strategic vision of the internationalization of education has been formalized into a systemic national document by the countries of the European Union and developed countries; at present, developing countries and Asian countries are catching up with them. To date, out of 22 countries that have developed national strategies for the internationalization of higher education, 14 are located in Europe (Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Latvia, the Netherlands, Poland, Spain, Switzerland, Sweden, Great Britain, Norway), five are in Asia (Japan, Kazakhstan, South Korea, Malaysia, Singapore). The most developed internationalization strategies are represented by Australia and Germany. Countries that have development strategies for the internationalization of

higher education, accumulate more than 40% of foreign students in their territory [7].

The first national strategy for the internationalization of education - the National Strategy and Council for International Education - appeared in Germany in 2008. As part of the implementation of this strategy, the German government set itself the goal of attracting 350 thousand foreign students by 2020, but already in 2017 this figure was exceeded and amounted to 358.9 thousand people.

In 2017, the strategy was amended to meet modern trends in international education and aimed at strengthening cooperation with developing countries, digitalization, further development of research infrastructure and creation of global innovation centers.

Australia's National Strategy for International Education 2025 aims to attract "fee-paying" international students. By 2025, this figure should increase by 45%. The main goal of the UK Strategic plan - World leading impact, adopted in 2019, is to increase the number of international students by more than 30% and education export revenues to 35 billion pounds. Art. The key tool for attracting foreign students as part of the implementation of this strategy is the introduction of the right of students to work for territory of the United Kingdom [7]. The only country that does not have a formed policy, but occupies a leading position in terms of the level of internationalization in the global educational arena, is the United States. First of all, this is due to the fact that the responsibility for higher education does not lie at the state level, but at the level of state administration [4].

The ratio of the number of foreign students and the total number of all university students in the universities of the world, according to the Times Higher Education World University Rankings, averages from 20 to 40%, and in some of them - even more in developed countries - more than 20%. In the world today, a real competitive struggle has unfolded for foreign students entering mainly natural science and technical specialties. Global research universities in the US, Canada, the UK and Germany are particularly active in it.

In order to attract foreign personnel, countries seek to conditions for admission, study and living in their territory are more attractive. For example, in France, education in all public universities is free for both citizens of the country and foreigners. The German government provides a large number of scholarships for international students, such as the DAAD14 scholarship. You can get a US university degree for free by winning a Fulbright Foundation grant that covers all expenses for tuition, transportation and passing the TOEFL exam. There are four types of funding for international students in China: Chinese Government Scholarships, Local Government Scholarships, Confucius Institute Scholarships, and Enterprise Scholarships.

Changes in the trends of international academic mobility, as well as the need to solve the tasks set by the Latvian government to attract talented foreign applicants, have actualized the issue of building a new communication strategy aimed at the use of digital

technologies [7]. Building strong presence on the Internet, with visibility on an international scale, should become one of the main tasks of Latvian universities in the context of a massive transition to distance learning. The implementation of this task involved not only the identification of channels for disseminating information and tools for communication with the user, but also the management of digital media, the creation of a digital brand of the university, and the constant analysis of the target audience and competitors, analysis of the information field and analytics of the university product line, content marketing, trigger communications, targeted and native advertising, SEO promotion and media planning. Potential foreign applicants, who today need to be attracted to study at Latvian universities, are part of generation Z. This is the first truly digital generation for which “smart” technologies are becoming common social practices [5, 6]. Generation Z is always connected. It is important for them not to miss the moment and to be in constant interaction. They spend more than five hours a day online and check for updates every 30 minutes. To express feelings and emotions, they use a special language - stickers, videos, gifs and emoji. Another important characteristic of Generation Z is that they are visuals. Online video becomes for them the main source of not only entertainment, but also the search for information. They prefer engaging content, they are active and willing to share and comment on videos and posts that meet their interests.

Taking into account the characteristics of the potential target audience and the phenomena associated with the pandemic, Latvian universities are gradually integrating “traditional” types of marketing communications with online promotion technologies. The main channel of information for foreign applicants is the university website in foreign languages. To achieve a high level of Internet positioning in the international educational space, universities will be helped by the constant creation of content that is attractive to a particular consumer and the establishment of SMM communication that complies with the principles of transmedia and personification [2]. To do this, the foreign language version of the site should contain only the content that is relevant for potential foreign students, and the information should be available on all mobile devices. If we rank the types of content depending on the goal (to provide awareness of the university brand or stimulate the purchase of an educational service), the content can be:

- entertaining (emotional impact on the target audience in order to inform about the brand of the university): games, tests, viral content, virtual tours, videos. Such content will help to establish emotional contact with a foreign target audience. Video is the most popular content of the new generation of students. They post their own videos, comment on the videos of opinion leaders and bloggers, and share their favorite videos. Therefore, the placement of video content on the pages of the site will increase its attendance by potential students. According to statistics, viewing the pages of the site increases. It improves by 48% if it contains high-quality visual content [8]. Thus, a virtual tour of the campus will allow foreign students to see the space for recreation and study at the university, and the student’s

video content from lectures and practical classes in scientific laboratories will introduce the features of the educational process and encourage them to fill out application forms and register on the site. That is why it is very important to place video content on the pages with information about the procedure and rules receipts;

- inspiring (emotional impact to stimulate the purchase of educational services): reviews and reviews of graduates - brand ambassadors, their opinions and recommendations on forums and in communities can become a means of attracting potential applicants. Statistics show that the younger generation, when choosing an educational trajectory, does not trust the brand of the university more in general, but the opinion and recommendations of students and graduates of the university. In this regard, it is necessary to delegate the function of communication with the target audience to those who tell stories as much as possible;

- educational (rational impact in order to get the target audience acquainted with the university): press releases, infographics, trends reviews, interviews with key speakers of the university. Modern Users The Internet prefers a graphical way of presenting information. Using infographic elements, you can visually present complex information or clearly delineate the stages of a multi-stage process, such as applying to a university;

- persuasive (rational impact to stimulate the purchase of educational services): webinars, interactive presentations and exhibitions, online calculators, checklists, practical cases for admission or passing creative exams. The main task when using such marketing tools is to conduct prompt consultations for foreign applicants when submitting documents, filling out a personal account, collecting the necessary documents upon admission and enrollment, and reducing tension among applicants [8].

Social networks are the main platform for communication with potential students. For the widest involvement of the consumer of educational services when using a marketing tool in social networks, Latvian universities it is necessary to choose niche placements based on the national language and cultural characteristics. An equally significant element in attracting foreign applicants is the use of big data and artificial intelligence. Universities are increasingly using conversational applications such as chatbots that respond to specific a pool of questions and passing non-standard questions to specialists that require personal participation. Contextual advertising is the most effective way to communicate with potential applicants. Such advertising is organically and logically woven into the content of the site on which it is placed, and causes a high credibility among the target audience. Another common marketing mechanism is targeting (targeting) - a tactic that allows you to distribute information to certain group of Internet users. When entering foreign markets, cooperation with bloggers can also become an effective channel for attracting potential students. On average, 30% of young users trust the opinions and recommendations of bloggers. However, without knowledge of local specifics, universities run the risk of spending their mar-

keting budget inefficiently. It can be stated with confidence that in order to withstand high competition in the global education market, the struggle for talented foreign applicants, Latvian universities need to actively implement international digital marketing activities. Wherein it must be remembered that in order to achieve the goals set by the government, it is important not only to increase the volume of exports of educational services, but also to restructure the export portfolio towards the research track. In recent years, the export of education in Latvia has come to be regarded as an important tool for attracting talented, solvent and strong foreign applicants from other countries as a significant source of income, a way to improve the reputation of national universities in the global educational space.

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